

Supporting Information for “Spatiotemporal Gaussian Process Regression Advances Early Detection of Precipitation Emergence”

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Supplementary Table 1. List of CMIP6 models used in this study. Model metadata, including institutional affiliations, country of origin, and atmospheric resolution, are obtained from the official CMIP6 database (https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/CMIP6_CVs/docs/CMIP6_source_id.html).

Model	Institution	Country	Atm. Res. (km)
ACCESS-CM2	CSIRO-ARCCSS	AUS	250
ACCESS-ESM1-5	CSIRO-ARCCSS	AUS	250
AWI-CM-1-1-MR	AWI	DEU	100
BCC-CSM2-MR	BCC	CHN	100
CAMS-CSM1-0	CAMS	CHN	100
CAS-ESM2-0	CAS	CHN	100
CESM2-WACCM	NCAR	USA	100
CMCC-CM2-SR5	CMCC	ITA	100
CMCC-ESM2	CMCC	ITA	100
CanESM5	CCCma	CAN	500
E3SM-1-1	DOE	USA	100
EC-Earth3	EC-Earth-Consortium	EU	100
EC-Earth3-CC	EC-Earth-Consortium	EU	100
EC-Earth3-Veg	EC-Earth-Consortium	EU	100
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR	EC-Earth-Consortium	EU	250
FGOALS-f3-L	CAS	CHN	100
FGOALS-g3	CAS	CHN	250
FIO-ESM-2-0	FIO-QLNM	CHN	100
GFDL-CM4	NOAA-GFDL	USA	100
GFDL-ESM4	NOAA-GFDL	USA	100
IITM-ESM	CCCR-IITM	IND	250
INM-CM4-8	INM	RUS	100
INM-CM5-0	INM	RUS	100
IPSL-CM6A-LR	IPSL	FRA	250
KACE-1-0-G	NIMS-KMA	KOR	250
KIOST-ESM	KIOST	KOR	250
MIROC6	MIROC, JAMSTEC	JPN	250
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MPI-M, DKRZ, DWD	DEU	100
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	DKRZ, DWD, MPI-M, AWI	DEU	250
MRI-ESM2-0	MRI, JMA	JPN	100
NESM3	NUIST	CHN	250
NorESM2-MM	NCC	NOR	100
TaiESM1	NTU	TWN	100

Supplementary Figure 1. Spatial distribution of intermodel variance for standardized 5 year precipitation anomalies.

Supplementary Figure 2. Same as in Figure 2 but using data up to 2000 as “observed” period

Supplementary Figure 3. Same as in Figure 2 but using data up to 2040 as “observed” period

Supplementary Figure 4. Fraction of posterior observations within predicted confidence bounds for CMIP6 MMM, UGPR, CGPR, and SGPR. Predictions were made for all 33 CMIP6 GCMs at each grid point using observations up to 2020. Violin plots show the distribution of fractions, with the black box marking the interquartile range and the white dash the median. The dashed line denotes the 0.68 reference level.

Supplementary Figure 5. Weighed global mean fraction of global area that predicts the correct emergence (green), incorrect emergences (red) and no emergence (gray) while using (a) CMIP6 MMM, (b) CGPR conditioned on data up to 2000, (c) 2050, and (d) 2070.

Supplementary Figure 6. Weighed global mean fraction of global area that predicts the correct emergence (green), incorrect emergences (red) and no emergence (gray) while using (a) CMIP6 MMM, (b) SGPR conditioned on data up to 2000, (c) 2050, and (d) 2070.